

Multi-, inter-, and transdisciplinary approaches to nature-based flood risk management

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Abstract

Nature-based solutions (NBS) can act as a valuable complement to conventional 'grey' infrastructure for stormwater management (e.g. dams and dikes) in reducing flood risks as these 'green' solutions are perceived to be more flexible and multi-functional. However, to achieve effective NBS, a multi-actor approach in developing appropriate measures for specific sites is required as NBS occupy more space than 'grey' infrastructure and often overlap with private land. NBS also necessitate a multidisciplinary approach, to maximise environmental, social, and economic benefits. Thus, a transdisciplinary approach is needed for the effective implementation of NBS. Viewing NBS as a boundary concept, focusing on the common ground for different disciplines and actors, can facilitate communication and provide a first step towards effective flood risk mitigation.

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Introduction

When dealing with the increased risk of flooding caused by climate change and human interventions in global landscapes, conventional 'grey' infrastructure (e.g. dams and dikes) is no longer adequate to respond to current rates of land use changes and increasing frequency of weather extremes [1]. Therefore, such infrastructure must be complemented with nature-based solutions (NBS) [2]. NBS are measures "inspired by, supported by or copied from nature" [3]. Nature-based flood risk management involves multiple stakeholders and disciplines since it requires 1) implementation on a large scale; 2) occupation of private land; and 3) a holistic approach to maximise co-benefits [4]. Due to the multifunctionality of NBS, they often combine flood reduction solutions with other co-benefits such as microclimate regulation, mitigate soil erosion, support air and water purification, and enhance carbon sequestration or support biodiversity [2]. Examples of NBS include floodplain restoration [5] or the implementation of small ponds [6]. To have a relevant effect in flood risk reduction, NBS should comprise interconnected small-scale measures across catchments, rather than large isolated measures [7].

There is increasing political interest in applying the NBS approach in flood risk management, but barriers to a wider NBS implementation have been identified by experts from various disciplines (Raška, Bezak) [8]. These include limited knowledge on the effectiveness of NBS in flood risk mitigation, complicated decision-making in NBS placement, conflicts between multiple land uses and associated challenges related to limited availability of land, and complex governance constraints. Theoretically, hydrological processes determine the most appropriate locations for effective implementation of NBS, but access to these locations is often dependent on the landowners [9]. However, these landowners are

not necessarily the implementing actors and may be not willing to make their land available and forego potential profits deriving from current and future land use [10]. Access to private land is thus pivotal for the implementation of NBS. This shifts the NBS implementation discourse from the government agencies dominating flood risk management to a situation where private actors are also responsible for implementation [11,12].

NBS call for a transdisciplinary approach

To gain access to land for the implementation of NBS, many landowners need to participate. Different stakeholders may have their own perceptions on land use and on implementation of NBS [13], and conflicts between these stakeholders can undermine effective implementation [14]. Additionally, land use and ownership constraints, as well as biophysical, economic, social, and operational constraints challenge the implementation of NBS [8,15,16]. Examples include issues of effectiveness of NBS on the hydrological system, costs of implementation and maintenance, issues of responsibility, or conflicts of land use and property rights [4,8]. Therefore, implementation requires cooperation between many actors and disciplines. For successful implementation, flood risk management needs to take a comprehensive approach, mobilising multiple disciplines, stakeholders, and their interests and coordinating their ambitions and actions [17]. Examples of discipline stakeholders required to develop effective NBS include water managers, landowners, engineers, hydrologists, geographers, ecologists, soil scientists, sociologists, lawyers, and economists. Approaches where this transdisciplinary approach is required include, for example, 1) developing cost–benefit calculations for the financial compensation for using land for NBS [18];

2) identifying land policy instruments for the mobilisation of private land without intervening in the property rights [19]; 3) combining hydrological and financial knowledge in tailored risk advice to homeowners [20]; and appropriate design to support several species [21]. Integration of the different disciplines represented requires stakeholders to move beyond their own field, creating new governance arenas [4].

This can be perceived as a multidisciplinary challenge as different disciplines have their own perceptions on land use and requirements on NBS design for different ecosystem services [2]. To overcome this challenge, Raška et al. call for transdisciplinary action when implementing NBS. According to Ferreira and Kalantari [4], there are three key ways in which multiple disciplines can be brought together in nature-based flood risk management (see Figure 1):

- A *multidisciplinary* approach entailing multiple disciplines working side-by-side on a shared topic, each within the boundary of their discipline.
- An *interdisciplinary* approach entailing joint action by multiple disciplines to deal with complicated problems, integrating knowledge from multiple disciplines to design collaboratively a framework, using a united language.
- A *transdisciplinary* approach entailing full synergy of multiple disciplines in a new overarching discipline, aiming to solve highly complex environmental, economic, and societal problems.

At present, nature-based flood risk management typically uses a multidisciplinary approach, by involving, e.g.

Figure 1

Three ways in which multiple disciplines/stakeholders can cooperate in nature-based flood risk management. Some examples of stakeholders are indicated. Other relevant disciplines include e.g. hydrology, geography, law, sociology, and engineering. Based on Darian-Smith and McCarty [25].

risk management and planners operating within their disciplinary borders [4]. However, a transdisciplinary approach is required for effective mitigation of the risks of flooding, which in turn requires ways of dealing with the tensions and synergies of involving multiple disciplines and stakeholders in NBS and flood risk management.

NBS as a boundary concept

Different stakeholders interpret NBS in different ways, based on their needs and ambitions. For example, hydrologists and engineers perceive NBS as a way to reduce flood risk, geographers observe the capacity of NBS to mitigate floods from a spatial perspective, ecologists focus on the impact of vegetation in flood retention, soil scientists consider the role of soil in retaining water, sociologists assess the impact of NBS in reducing the social impacts of floods, economists focus on the cost-effectiveness and efficiency of NBS as ways to address risk, and lawyers consider legal implications of NBS and compliance with regulations to reduce flood risk. These different perceptions make NBS a rather flexible and vague concept that can have multiple meanings, with no common understanding. In an alternative approach, NBS can be perceived as a boundary concept that facilitates communication across disciplinary borders by focusing on the common ground between disciplines and creating a shared vocabulary, even though the meaning of terms may differ between specific disciplines [22]. Boundary concepts become successful if they “enhance the salience, credibility and legitimacy of the information they produce” [23]. They thereby promote dialogue and translation of concepts between multiple dimensions and actors, between experts and decision-makers, and between spatial scales. In fact, boundary concepts initiate an iterative communication process of co-creation that is open for communication, translation, and mediation between different disciplines [23].

Perceiving NBS as a boundary concept provides the opportunity for disciplines to focus on common ground and collaborate, without compromising their own interests and ambitions. As various disciplines and actors involved in the implementation of NBS perceive these solutions differently, use of NBS as a boundary concept is helpful to support a shared understanding among disciplines and groups [23]. Disciplines are then able to bridge interests and ambitions across their multiple boundaries, leading to consensus. This can form a first step towards an interdisciplinary (and later transdisciplinary) approach to NBS, not only for flood risk management but also for other climate risks and environmental degradation problems.

Recent research provides some preliminary examples of what such collaborations could comprise, e.g.

intermunicipal upstream–downstream negotiations [24] and cooperation between flood risk managers and local farmers and foresters on leaky dams [14].

Concluding remarks and new research directions

Effective implementation of NBS for flood risk reduction requires collaboration between multiple actors, including flood risk managers and landowners, and expertise from multiple disciplines. However, the various interpretations and understandings of NBS may create barriers to implementation. Perceiving NBS as a boundary concept would facilitate communication between various actors and disciplines, helping to overcome these barriers.

For nature-based flood risk management to become truly effective, a transdisciplinary approach must be applied, where the creation of common governance arenas should be a primary goal. To increase salience, research should focus on the relevance of NBS for decision-makers, while to increase credibility, it should seek to demonstrate why NBS are effective and efficient in their allocation. To increase legitimacy, research should focus on the values and beliefs of stakeholders. Therefore, research needs to identify the common ground on NBS across multiple disciplines and stakeholders and to develop bridging concepts, a shared and understood vocabulary, commonly accepted rules and procedures, and a shared vision on how to deal with flood risk. Examples of such research avenues include 1) exploring the complex causal effects of NBS on climate risks and economic and social side-effects and 2) identifying strategies to mobilise land for NBS. This will require time and patience, but focusing on common ground, overlaps, or complementary approaches between disciplines can advance the development of the necessary transdisciplinary approach to NBS. The multi-, inter-, and transdisciplinary NBS framework is presented here in the context of flood risk management, but it can also be effective for reducing other climate risks and land degradation problems.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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